

Highly efficient, mild, one pot synthesis of 2-substituted benzimidazoles, benzothiazoles and pyridoimidazoles promoted by *N*-iodosuccinimide[†]

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Abstract : A common and highly efficient metal-free route for the synthesis of 2-substituted benzimidazoles, benzothiazoles and pyridoimidazoles from suitable 1,2-difunctionalised aromatic compounds and various aromatic and aliphatic aldehydes and ferrocenecarboxaldehyde was developed using *N*-iodosuccinimide as the oxidizing agent. The methodology involved very short reaction time, mild reaction procedure and easy work-up as well as excellent yields of the products.

Keywords : Benzimidazoles, benzothiazoles, pyridoimidazoles, *N*-iodosuccinimide, ferrocenecarboxaldehyde, (±)-citronellal.

Introduction

Benzimidazoles and benzothiazoles are very important organic scaffolds due to their outstanding biological activities¹. They have wide range of applicability as antibacterial², antimicrobial³, antiulcers⁴, potential anxiolytics⁵, antitumor⁶ and anticancer⁷ agents. Moreover, benzimidazoles and its derivatives and also pyridoimidazoles have currently been applied in corrosion science⁸, fluorescence⁹, chemosensing¹⁰, crystal engineering¹¹ and ABPBI membranes¹². So, developments of new synthetic routes, which would render new products containing these heterocyclic motifs, are of considerable importance to library of benzimidazoles, benzothiazoles and pyridoimidazoles. Some interesting and important compounds containing benzimidazole, benzothiazole and pyridoimidazole moieties are listed in Fig. 1.

In case of benzimidazole syntheses, previously employed methods involved the reaction between 1,2-phenylenediamines and aromatic and aliphatic carboxylic acids or their derivatives (nitriles, amidates or orthoesters) in the presence of strong acids such as polyphosphoric acids or mineral acids and the thermal or acid-catalysed

Fig. 1. Examples of some important compounds.

cyclisation of *N*-(*N*-arylbenzimidoyl)-1,4-benzoquinone-imines^{1a}. The most popular method for constructing 2-substituted benzimidazole and benzothiazole rings was the cyclocondensation of suitable 1,2-difunctionalised aromatic compounds with a wide range of aromatic and aliphatic aldehydes in the presence of an oxidising agent or via aerial oxidation under the reaction conditions employed^{1a}. Examples of oxidising agents recently applied included metal salts and complexes, viz. nanosized Mn(acac)₃ anchored aminofunctionalised silica^{13a}, Co(OH)₂/CoO in solid state^{13b}, Al₂O₃/KF^{13c},

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

$\text{Fe}(\text{HSO}_4)_3$ ^{13d}, FeF_3 in water^{13e}, CuO nano-particles supported on silica^{13f} etc. and other inorganic and organic agents viz. silica sulfuric acid^{14a}, $(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4/\text{Br}_2$ under MW^{14b}, 2,4,6-trichloro-1,3,5-triazine^{14c} and iodosobenzene diacetate^{14d} etc. Reactions were reported to occur with thiamine hydrochloride in DMF^{15a}, Indion-190 resin^{15b}, animal bone meal^{15c}, hydrotrope in water^{15d} and also in aqueous glycerol under refluxing condition^{15e}.

Some of the methodologies mentioned here had limitations like drastic reaction conditions, use of toxic reagents or metal ions, lower yields with many side products, employing high temperatures, prolonged reaction time, laborious extraction and purification procedure as well as low to moderate range of applicability. Very few methods were available in literature which could be applied successfully for exclusive preparation of both 2-substituted benzimidazoles, benzothiazoles and pyridimidazoles. *N*-Bromosuccinimide (NBS) was extensively used as oxidizing agent in many reactions¹⁶, but oxidizing capability of *N*-iodosuccinimide (NIS) was not explored to that extent¹⁷. Moreover, *N*-halosuccinimides (generally NBS, as it is cheaper) in dichloromethane were tried for cyclocondensation reaction of aliphatic 1,2-diamines with aromatic aldehydes for overnight stirring at room temperature leading to comparable yields of 1,2-dihydroimidazoles¹⁸. In our present work, a unique reagent system had been developed for the preparation of those three heterocycle derivatives under mild conditions in shorter reaction time from respective 1,2-difunctionalised aromatic and heterocyclic compounds reacting with a variety of aromatic and aliphatic aldehydes. The procedure confirms that NIS is more efficient as organic oxidant than NBS for this type of cyclocondensation reaction. Moreover, NIS is physiologically safer than NBS as it serves "active iodine" to the thyroid¹⁹.

Results and discussion

A set of reactions with *ortho*-phenylenediamine (*o*-PD, **1a**) and benzaldehyde (**2a**) as model compounds using NBS and NIS as oxidizing agents in different solvents and reaction conditions were carried out when 2-substituted benzimidazoles (**3aa**) was isolated as major products alongwith 1,2-disubstituted benzimidazoles (**4aa**) as side-products (Scheme 1). The results of those experiments are summarized in Table 1.

For initial study, the reaction between *o*-PD (**1a**, 1 mmol) and benzaldehyde (**2a**, 1 mmol) in water using NBS (1.2 mmol) as oxidant at room temperature was undertaken, which formed a mixture of **3aa** : **4aa** (70 : 20) within 3 min (entry 1). The same reaction in aqueous K_2CO_3 (entry 2) and CTAB-water (entry 3) gave product ratio **3aa** : **4aa** as (60 : 32) and (78 : 10), respectively. In aqueous dioxane, the yield of side-product **4aa** was increased to 30% (entry 4). Employing acetonitrile as solvent, **3aa** was isolated as the single product (88%, entry 5), whereas in acetonitrile-water mixture in presence of K_2CO_3 , the formation of 1,2-disubstituted **4aa** could not be prevented (12% yield, entry 6). Formation of 1,2-disubstituted benzimidazoles alongwith the 2-substituted derivatives in highly polar aqueous or aquated solvent medium could be rationalised due to early formation of the diimine derivatives²⁰ which oxidatively cyclised to imidazole ring. Satisfied with the results involving NBS as oxidant, similar set of reactions were tried using NIS (1.2 mmol) as oxidizing agent (entries 7–14). An excellent yield of **3aa** (95%, entry 11) was obtained within 5 min in acetonitrile as solvent. Increasing the amount of NIS to 1.5 mmol had only marginal effect (entry 13) and lowering its amount to 1.0 mmol, resulted in extended reaction time (42 min) and lower yield of **3aa** (78%, entry 12). When NIS was adsorbed on silica to increase the surface area of the oxidant, refluxing in acetonitrile

Scheme 1. Synthesis of 2-substituted benzimidazole (**3aa**) and 1,2-disubstituted benzimidazole (**4aa**) from *o*-PD (**1a**) and PhCHO (**2a**).

Table 1. Optimization of the reaction condition^a

Entry	Catalyst (mmol)	Reaction condition	Time (min)	Isolated yield (%) (3aa : 4aa)
1	NBS (1.2)	H ₂ O, rt	3	70 : 20
2	NBS (1.2)	H ₂ O, K ₂ CO ₃ , rt	50	60 : 32
3	NBS (1.2)	CTAB-H ₂ O, rt	35	78 : 10
4	NBS (1.2)	Dioxane : H ₂ O, rt	3	58 : 30
5	NBS (1.2)	CH ₃ CN, rt	5	88
6	NBS (1.2)	CH ₃ CN : H ₂ O, K ₂ CO ₃ , rt	82	76 : 12
7	NIS (1.2)	H ₂ O, rt	3	76 : 20
8	NIS (1.2)	GTAB-H ₂ O, rt	18	85
9	NIS (1.2)	SDS-H ₂ O, rt	20	60
10	NIS (1.2)	Dioxane : H ₂ O, rt	3	70 : 20
11	NIS (1.2)	CH ₃ CN, rt	5	95
12	NIS (1)	CH ₃ CN, rt	42	78
13	NIS (1.5)	CH ₃ CN, rt	4	96
14	NIS-SiO ₂ (20 mol%)	CH ₃ CN, 90 °C	60	40 : 30

^aReactants (**1a**, **2a**) : 1 mmol each.

was necessary to obtain a mixture **3aa** : **4aa** : **1a** in the ratio 40 : 30 : 10 (entry 14). Though the reaction pathways followed the same pattern as in the case of NBS, when NIS was applied in aqueous medium (entries 7 and 9), exclusive formation of **3aa** (yield 85% and 60% in entries 8 and 9 respectively) was observed in shorter time than when experiments had been carried out in CTAB-H₂O and SDS-H₂O in variance with the results shown in entry 3. From these data, it was concluded that NIS as oxidant was more specific for this cyclodehydration step which was not explored earlier.

From Table 1, entry 11 was chosen as most suitable reaction condition on the basis of short reaction time with higher yield and exclusive formation of **3aa**. To generalize the procedure, different aromatic and aliphatic aldehydes and also ferrocenecarboxaldehyde were reacted with 3-methyl-*o*-PD (**1b**), 2,3-diaminopyridine (**1c**) and 2,3-diamino-5-bromopyridine (**1d**). In Table 2, the entire range of 2-substituted benzimidazoles synthesized is listed with eight new compounds. From Table 2, it was found that

the system worked very well with aromatic aldehydes bearing electron-donating (entries 2, 3, 9, 10 and 14) and electron-withdrawing (entries 4–8, 11, 12, 15, 17, 18) groups as well as ferrocenecarboxaldehyde (**2l**) (entries 13 and 19). For *p*-cyanobenzaldehyde a small amount of (8%) 1,2-disubstituted product was isolated (entry 8). As indicated in Table 2, the reactions involving *N,N*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (**2m**) (entry 14) and 2,3-diamino-5-bromopyridine (**1d**) (entries 16–20), heating to 40 °C was required to complete the reaction. The reagent system was well tolerated by the easily polymerisable and moisture sensitive aldehyde furfural (**2n**) (yield 48%, entry 20). The methodology was quite applicable to cyclocondensation between *ortho*-aminothiophenol (**1e**) and different aromatic aldehydes and also ferrocenecarboxaldehyde (**2l**) for the syntheses of various benzothiazoles and the results are summarized in Table 2 (entries 21–32).

We employed the same procedure to aliphatic aldehydes containing short chain (C₃) and long chain (C₁₀) of

Table 2. Results of NIS/CH₃CN promoted synthesis of 2-aryl/heteroaryl/ferrocenyl benzimidazoles, benzothiazoles and pyridoimidazoles (3)^a

Entry	Amino, 1	Aldehyde, 2	Products, 3, 4	Yield ^b (%)	Time (min)	Ref.
1				95	5	13a
2	1a			93	20	13a
3	1a			96	15	13a
4	1a			93	6	13a
5	1a			90	18	21
6	1a			88	29	13a
7	1a			82	40	13a
8 ^c	1a			70	42	22

Table-2 (contd.)

			8			
9	1a			79	40	23
10		2i		80	24	-
11	1b			91	6	-
12	1b			90	28	-
13	1b			82	10	26
14 ^d	1b			70	12	27
15		2j		76	10	28
16 ^d		2a		66	40	36
17 ^d	1d	2d		52	40	37

18 ^d	1d	2e		50	42	38
19 ^d	1d	2l		70	10	-
20 ^d	1d	2n		48	10	-
21		94	10	13a		
22	1e	2b		91	22	13a
23	1e	2d		93	18	13a
24	1e	2e		88	18	13a
25	1e	2f		81	31	13a
26	1e	2h		85	35	30
27	1e	2i		78	30	33
28	1e	2k		82	50	31
29	1e	2l		70	25	35
30	1e	2o		88	9	29

31	1e	 3ep	81	10	32	
32	1e	 3eq	67	22	34	

^aReaction conditions : **1** (1 mmol), **2** (1 mmol), NIS (1.2 mmol), CH₃CN (5 mL), rt, stir. ^bAll yields are isolated yield. ^c8% 1,2-Disubstituted product was isolated. ^dHeating to 40 °C was required.

carbon atoms and results are summarized in Table 3. Though in case of short chain aliphatic aldehyde like isobutyraldehyde (**2r**), the yield was poor (22%, entry 1), but for (±)-citronellal (**2s**), the isolated yield of the products was quite high (entries 2–4).

In the case of benzothiazoles, experiments with (±)-citronellal failed to yield any cyclocondensation product (entry 5), but for cinnamaldehyde (**2t**), the corresponding compound was isolated in a moderate yield (42%, entry 6).

Table 3. Results of NIS/CH₃CN promoted synthesis of 2-alkyl benzimidazoles, benzothiazoles and pyridoimidazoles (3)^a

Entry	Reaction		Products		Yield ^b (%)	Time (min)	Ref.
	Amino, 1	Aldehyde, 2	Products, 3 (4)	R₁ = aliphatic			
1	1a	 3ar		22	28	24	
2 ^c	1a	 3as		78	45	25	
			 4as		10	-	

3	1b	2s		80	50	-
4 ^d	1d	2s		65	35	-
5	1e	2s	-	-	31	-
6	1e		42	22	27	

^aReaction conditions : **1** (1 mmol), **2** (1 mmol), NIS (1.2 mmol), CH₃CN (5 mL), rt, stir. ^bAll yields are isolated yield. ^c10% 1,2-Disubstituted product was isolated. ^dHeating to 40 °C was required.

Conclusion

A new highly efficient, mild and metal-free methodology had been developed for exclusive syntheses of both 2-substituted benzimidazoles and benzothiazoles in excellent yields using physiologically safe oxidizing agent *N*-iodosuccinimide and much less toxic acetonitrile as solvent within short reaction times (5–60 min) involving easy reaction procedure at ambient temperature.

Experimental

General :

All chemicals and solvents were purchased from Merck (Germany) and Sigma-Aldrich and were used without further purification. AR grade acetonitrile was dried over molecular sieves (4 Å) prior to use. Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes on Kofler block apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr discs with a Perkin-Elmer RXI FT-IR spectrophotometer. NMR spectra (¹H and ¹³C) were recorded in CDCl₃, DMSO-*d*₆ or CD₃CN solution in 5 mm BBO probe fitted with a pulse field gradient and working with Topspin 1.3 programme in a Bruker AV-300 Supercon NMR spectrometer (chemical shifts in δ ppm and *J* in Hz). Mass spectrometry was performed on a Q-Tof Micromass Waters Limited mass spectrometer. Elemental analyses for C, H and N were obtained by a Heraeus CHN-O-Rapid analyzer. Both column chromatography and TLC were done with silica gel.

Typical procedure for the synthesis of 2-substituted benzimidazoles (Table 2, entry 1) :

A solution of *o*-PD (108 mg, 1 mmol) and benzaldehyde (106 mg, 1 mmol) in 5 mL acetonitrile was stirred for 5 min. Then NIS (270 mg, 1.2 mmol) was added slowly and stirring was continued at room temperature for another 5 min. After completion of the reaction (TLC), the solvent was evaporated under vacuum. The reaction mixture was dissolved in ethyl acetate and the solution was washed successively with aqueous sodium bisulfite, water, aqueous sodium bicarbonate and water. The organic layer was then dried over sodium sulfate and solvent was removed under reduced pressure using an Eyela rotary evaporator. Concentrated reaction mixture was subjected to column chromatography using silica gel (100–200 mesh, Merck) and eluted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80 °C) and ethyl acetate mixture of increasing polarities to obtain 2-phenylbenzimidazole as the only product. In the case of 2-substituted benzothiazoles and 2-substituted pyridoimidazoles, the same procedure indicated above was followed. For all known compounds m.p.s were verified by comparing with those reported earlier (see references in Tables 2 and 3). Characterizations of some unknown benzimidazoles are listed below.

2-(Benzo[*d*][1,3]dioxol-5-yl)-4-methyl-1H-benzo[*d*]imidazole (3bi) :

Light yellow crystalline solid; yield 202 mg (80%),

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m.p. 144–145 °C (EtOH); IR (KBr) : ν 3431, 3000, 2900, 1464, 1240, 1034 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 2.50 (3H, s), 5.93–5.95 (2H, m), 6.79–6.87 (2H, m), 6.93–6.99 (1H, m), 7.26–7.29 (1H, m) 7.63–7.67 (2H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 17.3 (CH₃), 102.0 (CH₂), 107.0 (CH), 109.1 (2 \times CH), 121.5 (CH), 122.4 (CH), 122.8 (CH), 124.7 (C), 148.2 (3 \times C), 149.0 (2 \times C), 151.1 (C); TOF MS ES+, m/z (%) = 253.06 [M+1]⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₂N₂O₂ (252.08) : C, 71.42, H, 4.79, N, 11.10%. Found : C, 71.66, H, 4.40, N, 11.34%.

2-(4-Fluorophenyl)-4-methyl-1H-benzof[d]imidazole (3bj) :

Light yellow solid; yield 206 mg (91%), m.p. 200–202 °C (CH₂Cl₂); IR (KBr) : ν 3500, 3143, 1608, 1442, 1233, 840, 736 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.52 (3H, s), 6.98–7.04 (3H, m), 7.09 (1H, d, J 7.8 Hz), 7.38 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 7.96–8.00 (2H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃/DMSO- d_6) : δ 21.8 (CH₃), 117.3 (C), 120.3 (CH), 120.6 (CH), 127.1 (CH), 127.6 (CH), 129.9 (C), 131.5 (C), 133.7 (CH), 133.9 (2 \times CH), 155.4 (C), 166.0 (C), 169.5 (C); TOF MS ES+, m/z (%) = 227.06 [M+1]⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₁FN₂ (226.09) : C, 74.32, H, 4.90, N, 12.38%. Found : C, 74.66, H, 4.66, N, 12.31%.

2-(2,4-Dichlorophenyl)-4-methyl-1H-benzof[d]imidazole (3bk) :

Very pale yellow crystalline solid; yield 250 mg (90%), m.p. 138–140 °C (CH₂Cl₂); IR (KBr) : ν 3400, 3082, 2363, 1410, 1045, 840, 756 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.58 (3H, s), 7.04 (1H, d, J 7.5 Hz), 7.15 (1H, t, J 7.9 Hz), 7.30 (1H, dd, J_1 8.0, J_2 2.0 Hz), 7.42 (2H, m), 8.25 (1H, d, J 8.6 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 16.9 (CH₃), 123.4 (CH), 123.6 (CH), 127.2 (C), 127.6 (CH), 127.8 (C), 130.1 (CH), 130.2 (C), 131.6 (C), 133.0 (2 \times CH), 136.1 (2 \times C), 147.4 (C); TOF MS ES+, m/z (%) = 277.00 [M+1]⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₀Cl₂N₂ (276.02) : C, 60.67, H, 3.64, N, 10.11%. Found : C, 60.40, H, 3.70, N, 10.34%.

6-Bromo-2-(ferrocenyl)-3H-imidazo[4,5-b]pyridine (3dl) :

Orange solid; yield 266 mg (70%), m.p. >300 °C (CH₃CN); IR (KBr) : ν 2927, 1418, 1012, 815 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CD₃CN) : δ 4.17 (5H, s), 4.56 (2H, s),

5.04 (2H, s), 8.03 (1H, br m), 8.36 (1H, br m), 11.11 (1H, s); TOF MS ES+, m/z (%) = 381.97 [M+1]⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₂BrFeN₃ (380.95) : C, 50.30, H, 3.17, N, 11.00%. Found : C 50.66, H, 3.19, N, 11.34%; ^{13}C NMR spectra of this compound could not be performed due to its poor solubility even in CD₃CN.

6-Bromo-2-(furan-2-yl)-3H-imidazo[4,5-b]pyridine (3dn) :

Light brown crystalline solid; yield 127 mg (48%), m.p. 288–290 °C (EtOH); IR (KBr) : ν 2635, 1411, 1011, 886, 737 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 6.66 (1H, dd, J_1 3.3, J_2 1.8 Hz), 7.26 (1H, d, J 3.3 Hz), 7.83 (1H, d, J 1.8 Hz), 8.07 (1H, d, J 2.1 Hz), 8.30 (1H, d, J 2.1 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 117.6 (2 \times CH), 117.9 (CH), 118.1 (C), 130.4 (C), 149.2 (2 \times CH), 149.4 (C), 150.7 (C), 151.5 (C); TOF MS ES+, m/z (%) = 263.97 [M+1]⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₀H₆BrN₃O (262.96) : C, 45.48, H, 2.29, N, 15.91%. Found : C, 45.66, H, 2.09, N, 15.64%.

(±)-2-(2,6-Dimethylhept-5-en-1-yl)-1-(3,7-dimethyloct-6-en-1-yl)-1H-benzof[d]imidazole (4as) :

Yellow gummy solid; yield 38 mg (10%); IR (KBr) : ν 2917, 1458 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 0.92 (3H, d, J 6.6 Hz), 0.94 (3H, d, J 6.6 Hz), 1.25 (4H, m), 1.43 (3H, s), 1.45 (3H, s), 1.54 (3H, s), 1.56 (3H, s), 1.69 (4H, m), 1.93 (4H, m), 2.08 (2H, m), 2.58 (1H, dd, J_1 8.7, J_2 14.0 Hz), 2.77 (1H, dd, J_1 6.6, J_2 14.0 Hz), 5.00 (2H, m), 7.14 (2H, m), 7.19 (1H, m), 7.65 (1H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 17.6 (CH₃), 19.5 (2 \times CH₃), 19.6 (CH₃), 25.3 (CH₂), 25.5 (CH₂), 25.6 (2 \times CH₃), 32.5 (CH), 34.5 (CH), 34.9 (CH₂), 36.7 (2 \times CH₂), 37.2 (CH₂), 41.9 (CH₂), 109.1 (CH), 119.1 (CH), 121.6 (CH), 121.7 (CH), 124.1 (CH), 124.3 (CH), 131.4 (C), 131.6 (C), 134.8 (C), 142.7 (C), 154.0 (C); Anal. Calcd. for C₂₆H₄₀N₂ (380.32) : C, 82.05, H, 10.59, N, 7.36%. Found : C, 82.07, H, 10.57, N, 7.33%.

(±)-2-(2,6-Dimethylhept-5-enyl)-7-methyl-1H-benzof[d]imidazole (3bs) :

Yellow gummy solid; yield 205 mg (80%); IR (KBr) : ν 2919, 1440 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 0.93 (3H, d, J 6.6 Hz), 1.20–1.27 (1H, m), 1.40–1.47 (1H, m), 1.51 (3H, s), 1.61 (3H, s), 1.85–1.96 (2H, m), 2.15–2.17 (1H, m), 2.58 (3H, s), 2.74–2.82 (1H, m), 2.97–3.03 (1H, m), 4.95–4.99 (1H, m), 7.04 (1H, d, J

8.4 Hz), 7.13 (1H, d, J 7.8 Hz), 7.39 (1H, d, J 7.8 Hz), 10.68 (1H, br s); ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 17.3 (CH_3), 17.5 (CH_3), 19.5 (CH_3), 25.5 (CH_2), 25.5 (CH_3), 33.0 (CH), 37.0 ($2 \times \text{CH}_2$), 112.1 (CH), 122.0 (CH), 122.7 (CH), 124.2 (CH), 124.5 (C), 131.4 (C), 137.9 (C), 138.4 (C), 154.3 (C); TOF MS ES⁺, m/z (%) = 257.17 $[\text{M}+1]^+$; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2$ (256.19): C, 79.64, H, 9.44, N, 10.93%. Found: C, 79.66, H, 9.20, N, 10.74%.

(±)-6-Bromo-2-(2,6-dimethylhept-5-en-1-yl)-3H-imidazo[4,5-b]pyridine (3ds):

Brown gummy solid; yield 210 mg (65%); IR (KBr): ν 2926, 1420 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 1.08 (3H, d, J 6.6 Hz), 1.36 (1H, m), 1.41 (1H, m), 1.63 (3H, s), 1.68 (3H, s), 2.01 (2H, m), 2.28 (1H, m), 2.88 (1H, dd, J_1 8.4, J_2 14.0 Hz), 3.11 (1H, dd, J_1 6.6, J_2 14.0 Hz), 5.11 (1H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 8.20 (1H, d, J 1.8 Hz), 8.41 (1H, d, J 1.8 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 17.3 (CH_3), 19.2 (CH_3), 25.1 (CH_2), 25.3 (CH_3), 32.4 (CH), 36.6 (CH_2), 37.2 (CH_2), 112.9 (CH), 123.5 (CH), 128.5 (CH), 131.5 (C), 142.3 ($2 \times \text{C}$), 147.6 (C), 157.9 (C); Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{20}\text{BrN}_3$ (321.08): C, 55.91, H, 6.26, N, 13.04%. Found: C, 55.94, H, 6.23, N, 13.00%.

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